

Research paper

A comparison of temperature and freeze-thaw effects on high-swelling and low-swelling soils stabilized with xanthan gum

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ABSTRACT

Clay soils necessitate enhancement owing to their inadequate strength characteristics in geoen지니어ing. The utilization of biopolymers is a new bio-stabilization technique for clayey soils with no environmental disadvantages associated with traditional additives. The present research aims to evaluate the performance of varying concentrations of xanthan gum biopolymer (0.5, 1, and 2 %) concerning the strength and durability characteristics of two types of soil: kaolinite and bentonite, over varied curing time. For this purpose, tests were performed on compaction, compressive strength, free swelling, freezing and thawing, temperature effects, and microstructure to analyze the interaction between soil particles and biopolymer in both soils. The results indicated that the 1 % xanthan gum sample with a 28-day curing period had superior performance in both soil types, with a compressive strength enhancement of 457 % for kaolinite and 274 % for bentonite. The swelling test indicated that the optimal incorporation of biopolymer into kaolinite soil augmented swelling by 6 %, whereas the swelling of bentonite diminished up to 88 %. The freeze-thaw test demonstrated that as the number of cycles increased, the strength of the soil diminished; nevertheless, bentonite had a lesser decline in strength relative to kaolinite. Analysis of varying temperatures (40–70–100) revealed that optimal resistance performance in both soils occurs at 70 °C; however, the temperature's influence on the strength of stabilized bentonite is more pronounced. According to the findings, the addition of xanthan gum improves soil strength, hence increasing the feasibility of this stabilizer in practical applications such as landfills, embankments, and slopes.

1. Introduction

Kaolinite and bentonite soils are important geo-materials in the construction industry. Due to low shear and tensile strength, and volumetric change in clayey soils, it is essential to improve their mechanical performance [1]. Kaolinite and bentonite soils are among the most widely used types of soil [2,3]. Each of these soils falls under the category of clayey soils and needs improvement for building geo-structures. Bentonite is primarily composed of the mineral montmorillonite. Due to the structure of this mineral, bentonite soil has a high-water absorption capacity. In contrast, kaolinite soil experiences much more limited swelling due to the differences in its mineral structure. Moreover, kaolinite does not perform well under applied stresses, because of its looser structure. This indicates that both kaolinite and bentonite soils

require stabilization to address their weaknesses. Overall, the relationship between these clays' mechanical properties and stabilization techniques is fundamental for optimizing their use in the construction industry.

Generally, traditional stabilizers are used for stabilization of kaolinite and bentonite soils. Traditional stabilization methods involve using chemical additives such as fly ash, bitumen, lime, calcium, and cement [4–6]. Cement and lime can significantly reduce the plasticity of kaolinite and bentonite soils by facilitating chemical reactions that produce cementitious compounds, effectively binding soil particles together. The use of other calcium-based stabilizers serves to obtain a similar purpose, providing a strong bond and stability in soils that may otherwise be too weak for construction. While chemical additives provide several benefits, like improved efficiency, increased durability, and

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high strength at affordable costs [7], they have a permanent and detrimental effect on the ecosystem, environment and kaolinite and bentonite matrix [8]. For instance, cement is a material commonly used for soil stabilization, releasing around 1 ton of carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the environment for each ton produced [9–11]. The cement industry typically contributes 5 % of worldwide carbon dioxide emissions [9]. In addition, other conventional additives increase the stabilized soil's pH, affecting the quality of plants and groundwater [12]. Consequently, these chemical additives in improving kaolinite and bentonite soils have negative effects not only during their production but also during their operation, thereby impacting the natural ecosystem.

Currently, bio techniques are continuously employed to enhance the kaolinite and bentonite mechanical properties. These methods prioritize using sustainable and economical materials that are easy to use, durable, and eco-friendly [12–16]. Environmental considerations have led to a focus on utilizing natural polymers for stabilizing kaolinite and bentonite soils [14,17]. Living species, including plants, animals, and bacteria, are responsible for producing biopolymers. These materials are easily available and regarded as renewable resources [18]. Biopolymers exhibit substantially reduced carbon dioxide emissions compared to conventional stabilizers. Overall, methods of improving the mechanical properties of kaolinite and bentonite through biological methods can be categorized into i) bioclogging and ii) biocementation techniques. These techniques involve the direct injection of biopolymers into the soil or using organisms which make biopolymers that produce binding materials through microbial activity within the soil matrix [14,19]. Different biopolymers have been applied in clayey soil. However, the use of xanthan gum stands out because of its notable effects on kaolinite and bentonite soils with different engineering properties, drawing considerable interest [20–23]. Xanthan gum is a naturally occurring anionic polysaccharide produced through the fermentation of carbohydrates by the bacterium *Xanthomonas campestris*. The molecular formula for xanthan gum is C₃₅H₄₉O₂₉. The production of xanthan gum is achievable by the fermentation of industrial waste sugars, such as sucrose and fructose, by bacteria [24]. The essential composition of xanthan gum consists of repeating units formed by two glucose units, two mannose units, and one glucuronic unit collectively. The unique structure xanthan gum, characterized by a stiff rod-like helical configuration, exhibits insensitivity to temperature, pH, shear, and enzymatic degradation [25,26]. Moreover, it exhibits significant viscosity even at minimal concentrations along with pseudo-plastic characteristics. Considering its high viscosity, xanthan gum is commonly used as a compound in drilling muds in the oil and mining industries and as a fluid thickener in the food business. Recent studies have demonstrated the favorable capacity of this type of biopolymer for soil stabilization purposes [27–29]. Moreover, its anionic and hydrophilic characteristics promote interactions with cations and other polysaccharides (e.g., acetate, glucose, mannose, and potassium gluconate), thereby creating more robust hydrogels. These features make xanthan gum a suitable biopolymer for soil treatment [30,31].

Several investigations have been conducted on the influence of adding biopolymers on the mechanical characteristics and durability of soils. For instance, Galán-Marín et al. [32] assessed the ability of alginate biopolymers generated from seaweed for soil stabilization and reported comparable results to those achieved with lime and cement. Based on the results of this study and the abundance of seaweed in various regions, soils stabilized with alginate could be used as a substitute for soils stabilized with cement. Another research found that adding agar gum to sandy soil and increasing its concentration improved the compressive strength and stiffness of the stabilized samples. Additionally, the researchers found that the stabilizing effect of agar gel on sand particles can be greatly improved by adding a positively charged intermediary agent, such as modified starch [33]. In another effort, it was shown that the inclusion of xanthan gum in peat soil results in hydrogen or electrostatic interactions between xanthan gum and clay particles; hence, it modifies the overall structure of the soil. Introducing

this new structure enhances the cohesive forces within the soil fabric. However, the limitation of the mentioned study is the lack of evaluation of the durability of xanthan gum-stabilized soil [34]. Rashid et al. [35] showed that the shear strength of laterite soil was markedly enhanced with the addition of xanthan gum. They also found that 1.5 % is the most effective amount of xanthan gum for soil stabilization. In particular, the shear strength was reported to increase when the concentration of xanthan gum reached 1.5 %, while the effectiveness rate decreased. Nevertheless, in this study, microstructural analysis such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) tests were not considered. Another study investigated the impact of changing chitosan concentration, curing duration, and moisture content on the mechanical properties of treated samples. The performance of the samples was assessed using unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and direct shear tests. The results demonstrated that adding chitosan to clay soil increases particle adhesion, thus enhancing its mechanical characteristics. Nevertheless, this mechanism is affected by two primary factors, moisture and the duration of the curing process [36]. In the study performed by Ni et al. [22] the fatigue testing of clay samples revealed that the unmodified soil experienced failure at a stress level approximately similar to half of its compressive strength (55 to 60 % of the compressive strength). However, the soils treated with 3 % xanthan gum remained stable under the corresponding stress level. In addition, the fatigue life was enhanced irrespective of the loading schemes when the xanthan gum content was increased. In another study it was indicated that increasing the xanthan gum content in stabilized soil resulted in notable enhancements in the liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index. In addition it was proved that adding 5 % xanthan and a curing time of 5 days led to a significant enhancement in the UCS of the samples, increasing it from 234 to 399 kPa [37]. The study on the possibility of using xanthan gum to augment the stability of weak soils in subgrade layers showed that the soil's strength characteristics were considerably enhanced by incorporating xanthan gum as well as longer curing periods. Adding 1.5 % xanthan gum led to a significant increase in UCS and E50 values, rising by a factor of 5 to 7. However, in this study, the effect of temperature was not evaluated on the compressive strength of stabilized soil with xanthan gum. [38]. Performance analysis of soil stabilized with xanthan gum revealed that the compressive strength values declined by increasing the number of wet/dry cycles. However, the xanthan-stabilized samples demonstrated greater strength than the pure soil samples [39]. In another laboratory investigation, it was found that including xanthan gum in high-plasticity clays significantly enhanced their behavior. Specifically, adding xanthan gum resulted in a 4 to 9-fold increase in the UCS, strength improvement ratio, and the pure soil's energy absorption capacity. The mechanical strength improvement increased until a xanthan gum content of 5 %. Meanwhile, the highest enhancement in shear strength metrics was observed at a xanthan gum concentration of 1.5 % with a curing period of 60 days. The ultrasonic test to understand the compressive wave was not considered in this study [7]. In a laboratory study the impact of xanthan gum on the performance of bentonite and kaolinite soils was investigated. The UCS tests indicated that incorporating xanthan notably enhanced the compressive strength of both soils. It was found that the ideal amount of xanthan gum for bentonite and kaolinite soils was 1 % and 1.5 %, respectively after 28-day curing time. Furthermore, direct shear tests showed that the internal friction angle increased from 21 to 24 in bentonite and 12 to 17 for kaolinite after 28 days of curing when using the ideal percentage of xanthan gum. In this study, the impact of xanthan gum on the sample's durability and the influence of temperature on xanthan performance were not explored [40].

The review of previous studies shows that the durability of soil stabilized with xanthan gum has gained less attention. Also there has been a lack of emphasis on how xanthan gum affects the performance of both kaolinite and bentonite at the same time, particularly in terms of compressive wave velocity, swelling behavior, freeze-thaw performance, and temperature resistance. Since temperature changes have

significant effects on the mechanical behavior of xanthan stabilized soil, in this study, in addition to the comparative study of xanthan gum performance on the mechanical properties and durability of kaolinite and bentonite soils, the effect of temperature changes on the performance of stabilized soils has also been evaluated. Among the different biopolymers discussed earlier, Xanthan gum was demonstrated as the most efficient bio-material in enhancing the mechanical compressive and shear characteristics of kaolinite and bentonite soils. Apart from the literature review, the authors studied four biopolymers during trial pretests in this research. According to the results of UCS trial tests, xanthan gum is selected because of its exceptional performance and strong resistance to temperature and different pH levels. Hence, the present study provides a thorough comparative analysis on the effects of xanthan gum in stabilizing kaolinite soil (with a fairly low propensity for swelling) and bentonite soil (characterized by its high propensity for swelling). To this end, the stability of the treated soils was investigated through conducting a comprehensive analysis on their mechanical properties and durability under consecutive freeze-thaw (F-T) cycles. Additionally, the impact of different temperatures on the performance of xanthan gum was examined to assess its ability to enhance resistance. Furthermore, in the present research, the engineering performance and efficacy of xanthan-stabilized soil were compared in the two mentioned soil types. First, compaction tests were performed to assess the influence of xanthan gum on the soil's optimum moisture content and maximum dry density. Afterward, samples were produced at the optimum moisture content for UCS testing, ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) tests, durability assessments of stabilized soils under F-T cycles, and evaluations of temperature impacts. Finally, the soils and soil-biopolymer mixtures were subjected to microstructural analysis such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), XRD, and FTIR investigations.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Soil

Two soil types were analyzed to study the impact of soil type on soil stability through using xanthan gum. The bentonite used in this research

was a pure form obtained from the Kian Khak Iranian Company. It was described as a soil with extremely strong swelling properties. Fig. 1 represents the particle size distribution and provides a visual representation of the soil used for this purpose. Moreover, Table 1 and Table 2 show the soil's physical properties and detailed chemical compounds, respectively. The kaolinite soil used in the study was sourced from Arya Iranian Industrial Mining Company.

2.1.2. Xanthan gum

The xanthan gum used in this study was acquired from Afatos Company in Iran. Xanthan gum is a polysaccharide that has multiple applications in various industries. Xanthan gum is an anionic biopolymer that can absorb water molecules by forming hydrogen bonds and creating adhesive hydrogels [30]. Fig. 2 displays the molecular composition of xanthan gum. The xanthan gum is in a powdered state and has a cream color. Table 3 presents the physio-chemical properties

Table 1
Physical characteristics of the utilized soils.

Properties	Values		Standard	References
	Kaolinite	Bentonite		
Liquid limit (%)	37.8	291.3	ASTM D4318	[41]
Plastic limit (%)	19.1	54.6	ASTM D4318	[41]
Plasticity index (%)	18.7	236.7	ASTM D4318	[41]
Clay content (%)	100	100	ASTM D2487	[42]
Specific gravity	2.68	2.67	ASTM C127	[43]
Maximum dry density (MDD) (gr/cm ³)	1.59	1.355	ASTM D698	[44]
Optimum moisture content (OMC) (%)	23.63	32.4	ASTM D698	[44]
Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) (kPa)	185.9	456.3	ASTM D2166	[45]
Cohesion (kPa)	50.1	108.2	ASTM D3080	[46]
Friction (degree)	19.3	23.2	ASTM D3080	[46]

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution curve of the studied soils and xanthan gum.

Table 2
Chemical compositions of the kaolinite and bentonite.

Chemical composition	Percentage in weight (%)	
	Kaolinite	Bentonite
SiO ₂	56.66	53.89
Al ₂ O ₃	20.17	14.80
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.63	8.19
CaO	2.07	3.91
MgO	0.07	3.10
Na ₂ O	0.14	1.56
K ₂ O	0.23	0.40
TiO ₂	0.05	0.76
MnO	0.02	0.10
P ₂ O ₅	0.06	0.09
LOI	18.9	13.2

of xanthan gum used in this study.

2.2. Methods

This study examined the impact of xanthan gum on the strength characteristics and performance of bentonite and kaolinite soils during F-T cycles. The experiment involved testing two types of samples: 1) pure bentonite and kaolinite soil and 2) bentonite and kaolinite soil mixed with xanthan gum. Three concentrations of xanthan gum (0.5 %, 1 %, and 2 % of dry weight of soil) were used in this research. The selection range of xanthan gum was acquired through two methods. At first, the xanthan gum ratio was established according to the previous studies. The range of xanthan gum ratio in previous attempts was between 0.5 % to 3 % [47,48]. Moreover, prior research indicated that the most effective xanthan gum ratio for cohesive soils ranged from 1 to 2 %. In the second step, the UCS trial tests were carried out to identify the xanthan gum ratio which demonstrated a practical and effective range of 0.5 to 2 %. Moreover, the USC decreased after introducing more than 2 % of xanthan gum into the soils.

2.2.1. Sample preparation

According to earlier research, the soil and xanthan gum were combined in a dry state before the desired moisture was introduced to prepare the samples. The dry mixing of xanthan gum results in a uniform

dispersion inside the soil [47]. Previous research has indicated that the choice of preparation process for xanthan gum depends on its solubility and viscosity [47]. When 1 % xanthan gum is added to the soil, the concentration of xanthan gum in the soil measures around 1.7 % compared to water. This quantity surpasses the point at which dissolution occurs, which is 1.4 %. Hence, thorough dispersion of xanthan gum in water could not be achievable by wet mixing, potentially resulting in uneven distribution of xanthan gum in the soil [47,49,50]. The viscosity of xanthan gum at consumption doses of 0.5 %, 1 %, and 2 % is 644, 1621, and 2082 cps, respectively. The rise in viscosity caused by the elevated concentration of xanthan greatly diminishes the workability of xanthan-based mixtures, making it quite challenging to achieve uniform mixing with soil. For this reason, dry method was used. Fig. 3a shows the soil, xanthan gum, and their combination. To ensure consistency between soil particles and xanthan gum powder, the soil-xanthan gum mixture was first combined manually for 10 min. Then a mechanical blender was used for 5 min to achieve a uniform and homogeneous mixture. Furthermore, the visual examination was used to evaluate the uniformity of the mixture. The blending procedure persisted until a consistent color was obtained. Additionally, the use of a mechanical blender guaranteed the absence of flocculated particles. It is worth mentioning that the criteria for sample preparation were based on the dry density.

Table 3
Physio-chemical properties of xanthan gum.

Properties	Values/description
Color	Cream colored
Form	Powder
Origin	Bacteria
E number	415
Charge	Negative
Viscosity(cps)	1600–1650
pH	6.8
Average particle diameter (μm)	75
Molecular weight (g/mol)	239.23
Specific gravity	1.63
Water solubility	soluble

Fig. 2. Chemical structure of xanthan gum.

Fig. 3. The procedure of tests: (a) Mixing of xanthan gum and soil, (b) Experimental process.

2.2.2. Laboratory tests

Compaction tests were performed to determine the optimum moisture content of untreated soil and the soil treated with various amounts of xanthan gum. The tests were conducted following the procedure recommended for the standard proctor (ASTM D698 [44]). The soil's moisture content and dry density were determined at each step. The moisture level that gave the best results was used for the UCS and durability tests. The UCS test was performed following ASTM D2166 [45] standards on samples stabilized with OMC and MDD. During the experiment, the soil was subjected to a temperature of 110 °C for 24 h in an oven. After this period, once the soil had fully dehydrated, it was removed from the oven and permitted to attain ambient temperature. Subsequently, the xanthan gum and dry soil were combined, and water was introduced to attain the ideal level of moisture content. The resultant combination was compressed into a cylindrical mold measuring 38 mm in diameter and 76 mm in height. The prepared samples were kept in plastic containers at an ambient temperature of 23–25 °C with curing durations of 1, 7, 14, 28, and 56 days. After the curing period, the samples were tested to find the optimum percentage of biopolymer. They were loaded at a strain rate of 1.27 mm/min until they reached a maximum strain of 20 %.

The ultrasonic test was conducted according to ASTM C597–16 [51] to assess the impacts of different xanthan gum concentrations, curing time, and F-T cycles on the stiffness of the samples. Since the UPV testing is non-destructive, the samples made for UCS testing are used for conducting ultrasonic tests before the compressive strength test. Therefore, the samples used for ultrasonic testing are in solid form. In this process, the weights and the lengths of the samples were first determined. Then, the surfaces of UCS samples (bottom and top of samples) were lubricated before UPV to ensure proper acoustic coupling between the transducers and the soil sample. This improves signal transmission and the accuracy of ultrasonic measurements. Next, by using the CNS FARNELL PUNDIT device, ultrasonic waves were delivered at a frequency of 54 Hz through the UCS samples. Thus, the time taken for the compressive wave to pass through the sample was obtained. Afterward, by using Eq. (1) proposed by Mandal et al. [52], the velocity of the compressive wave (V_p) m/s through the sample was calculated. The stiffness values (D) MPa were determined using Eq. (2) suggested by Mandal et al. and Toohey & Mooney [52,53]:

$$V_p = \frac{l}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

$$D = \rho V_p^2 \quad (2)$$

where l represents the lengths (m) of samples, Δt represents the time (s) and ρ represents the density (kg/m^3) of samples.

A free swell test was performed as per ASTM D4546–14 [54] standards to examine the swelling behavior of kaolinite and bentonite soils. In this context, samples of unstabilized and stabilized soil measuring 5 cm in diameter and 0.5 cm in height were prepared and placed in a consolidation ring. In the free swell test, the compacted sample was entirely soaked in distilled water to facilitate the samples' free swelling.

The durability performance of the soil was examined by F-T cycle testing following ASTM D560 [55]. To conduct the F-T cycle, the samples utilized for the UCS tests were encased in two layers of sealed plastic bags to maintain their moisture content. In general, in the colder areas of the world, temperatures may drop to between –15 and –20 °C during the colder months, while in warm seasons maximum temperatures range from 22 to 30 °C in these areas. Consequently, temperatures ranging from –18 to 25 °C were taken into account to reflect real-world engineering situations [56,57]. Furthermore, for considering the worst scenario, the duration of the freezing cycle for each sample was 24 h. According to conducted studies [56,58], this amount of time is necessary to complete the formation of ice crystals and the melting of ice crystals at the aforementioned temperatures. In this study, soil samples were prepared by stabilizing them with 1 % xanthan gum, which was determined as the optimum proportion. The samples were then allowed to cure for 28 days. The samples experienced 1, 3, 5, 7, and 10 F-T cycles. Each freeze cycle included a 24-hour duration inside a freezer set at –18 °C. Also, each thaw cycle involved a 24-hour duration at room temperature ranging from 25 °C. Then, the samples were assessed for weight loss and changes in their compressive strength.

To investigate the impact of temperature, samples treated with 1 % xanthan gum were prepared similarly to the UCS samples. These samples were kept in an oven at 40, 70, and 100 °C for 28 days to examine the impact of temperature. Since the optimal temperature for the performance of biopolymer is between 10 and 70 °C [59,60], the mentioned range of was chosen. After elapsing the curing time, the prepared

samples underwent a UCS test [61]. It is worth mentioning that according to previous research the ideal temperature range for improving soil efficiency with biopolymer is between 10 and 70 °C [59]. The trial UCS test revealed that xanthan gum's bioactivity diminished after reaching 80 °C, hence impacting its efficacy in enhancing soil properties. Thus, the effect of 100 °C was investigated to assess the impact of high-temperature biopolymer resistance [62].

Furthermore, the microstructural behavior and potential interactions among the soil particles and xanthan gum were assessed by XRD, FTIR, SEM, and EDS analysis. For this purpose, the samples 1 cm in height were prepared according to the guidelines for sample preparation for UCS testing. Subsequently, microstructural images were taken using SEM and EDS (model MIRA3-TESCAN) at a magnification of 3000x. For XRD analysis, natural clay and stabilized soil samples were ground to obtain a uniform powder. This powder was then examined using a Philips PW-1730 diffractometer, scanning in the 2θ range from 10 to 80 °. Additionally, for FTIR testing, natural clay, and stabilized soil were completely milled to obtain a uniform powder for testing. The resulting powder was then analyzed using the AVATAR Thermo device. In all these microstructural tests, the samples were cured for 28 days. The methodology for carrying out the tests is shown in Fig. 3b.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Compaction characteristics

Fig. 4 provides the compaction graphs of kaolinite and bentonite

soils. As can be seen, increasing the xanthan gum concentration declined the kaolinite and bentonite dry density and increased the OMC. The creation of hydrogels and the addition of cross-linking agents at higher concentrations result in an expansion of pore space and a decrease in interactions among soil particles. Therefore, dry density further declines at higher concentrations [63]. The presence of xanthan gum hydrogel leads to the formation of ionic and hydrogen bonds between soil particles and xanthan gum, making the soil mass more uniform. On the other hand, as mentioned, the presence of xanthan gum increases the viscosity of the pore fluid. This leads to a decrease in the soil's sensitivity to a wider range of moisture levels and result in a smoother compaction curve for the stabilized soil. This trend becomes more noticeable by increasing the percentage of xanthan gum added (Fig. 4), due to the creation of a network of hydrogen bonds and cross-links, which make the soil matrix firmer and more resistant to compaction [12,26]. On the other hand, adding xanthan gum and its higher concentration also elevates the OMC because xanthan gum is hydrophilic [64]. Therefore, xanthan monomers have a greater affinity for water and create hydrogels [47]. Also, it enhances the capacity of soil particles to retain water (Fig. 4c and 4d). Increasing the xanthan gum content increases the viscosity of the soil's electrical double layer. This increment, in turn, strengthens the sliding resistance of soil particles. In addition, the soil structure undergoes flocculation, resulting in the entrapment of water particles inside the soil as revealed by SEM analysis [48]. The moisture content of bentonite soil increases significantly compared to kaolinite soil due to its flaky clay particle structure and higher specific surface area, resulting in enhanced water absorption.

Fig. 4. Compaction characteristics: Compaction curves of (a) Kaolinite, and (b) Bentonite; MDD and OMC trends for (c) Kaolinite and (d) Bentonite.

3.2. Unconfined compressive strength

Fig. 5a-j compare the stress-strain curves of untreated kaolinite and bentonite soils with stabilized kaolinite and bentonite soil with varying percentages of xanthan gum at various curing durations. As can be observed, the UCS values of the modified soils are noticeably greater than those of the untreated soils. This difference shows that increasing the xanthan gum content and the curing period increases soil strength. As can be seen the UCS of untreated and stabilized soils increases by prolonging the curing period. Over time, a greater proportion of the present silica reacts in untreated soils, gradually enhancing the soil's strength. The most significant enhancement in strength for the treated soils was reported at the end of 28 days. As the duration of the cure time increases from 28 to 56 days, the strength growth rate falls. According to Latifi et al. [40], most stabilizing biochemical processes occurred within 28 days. Adding xanthan gum up to a concentration of 1 % led to a considerable increase in the UCS of both bentonite and kaolinite-treated soils. After reaching this concentration level, the treated soils' compressive strength continues to increase, although at a slower rate. It is worth mentioning that, adding 1 % xanthan to bentonite, followed by a 28-day curing period, resulted in a 274 % increase in compressive strength (reaching 1712 kPa) compared to untreated bentonite. The percentage increase during the 28- to 56-day period was 47 %. In the same way, adding 1 % xanthan to kaolinite and allowing it to cure for 28 days resulted in a 457 % increase in UCS (reaching 1032 kPa) compared to untreated clay. There was a further 24 % enhancement in strength between curing days 28 and 56. Given that the comparable highest compressive strength was attained with 1 % xanthan and 2 % xanthan after 28 days of curing, 1 % xanthan was identified as the best concentration because of the reduced additive consumption and subsequent economic benefits.

The mechanism of bio-stabilization is shown in Fig. 6. Typically, strengthening stabilized soils can be linked to forming bio-cementitious (as will be proved by SEM and FTIR analysis) materials that bind soil particles together and occupy the empty spaces within the soil [40]. Xanthan gum's carboxyl (-COOH) groups can directly connect clay particles by creating cationic bridges and hydrogen bonds with the charged surfaces of soil particles. The results revealed that the stabilized bentonite has better strength than the stabilized kaolinite because of its stronger structure. However, the rise in strength with adding xanthan gum is considerably more significant in kaolinite than bentonite. This difference is due to the less compacted composition and increased ability to exchange cations of kaolinite soil, along with the stronger influence of the adhesive gel created by xanthan gum on it.

The secant modulus of kaolinite and bentonite soils can be estimated by analyzing the stress-strain curves and shown in Fig. 7. Secant Modulus is calculated at the 50 % of peak stress. Because unstabilized kaolinite and bentonite soils show less resistance and consequently have lower absorbed energy and peak stress, the values obtained for E_{50} for the unstabilized samples are significantly lower than the stabilized samples (Fig. 7). The secant modulus of kaolinite soil increased from 29.3 MPa in its original state to 216.9 MPa after being stabilized with 1 % xanthan gum during a curing period of 28 days. Similarly, the secant modulus of bentonite soil experienced a rise from 69.4 to 440.7 MPa when stabilized with a 1 % concentration of xanthan gum over 28 days. The results suggest that xanthan gum has a more significant impact on the secant modulus in bentonite soil, probably because of the greater stiffness of bentonite clay than kaolinite clay.

It should be noted that over time, the samples' failure strain decreases in both soil types. During the curing process, biopolymers transform from a gel state to a crystalline state, resulting in their hardening. This hardening causes the pore biopolymers to compress and become more durable, increasing their strength [65]. The failure strain of the samples generally decreases in both soil types as the curing period increases. However, when the curing time is 1 day, the failure strain of the samples increases with a higher concentration of xanthan gum.

Additionally, according to the data, the samples exhibit a more ductile failure because the xanthan gum hydrogels retain their hydration and do not undergo a phase transition within one day. The transition from a gel state to a crystalline state over time (as shown by XRD and SEM) results in the samples becoming more brittle and less ductile (Fig. 8). The 28 days of curing was used for failure pattern. In Fig. 8, it is evident that mixing xanthan gum with kaolinite and bentonite soils creates shear zones by forming bio-crystals between soil particles.

3.3. Swelling potential

Fig. 9 shows the influence of xanthan gum on the swelling characteristics of kaolinite and bentonite soils. As can be seen, adding xanthan gum to bentonite soil diminished its swelling but increased the swelling of kaolinite soil. Kaolinite soil has 1:1 clay mineral consisting of two distinct layered sheets: a tetrahedral silica sheet and an octahedral alumina sheet. These sheets are interconnected by shared oxygen and hydrogen atoms. The layer's asymmetry results in strong polarity and substantial dipole-dipole interactions. Therefore, the layers engage directly, creating platelets that are generally hexagonal. These platelets tend to aggregate, creating bigger platelets within the layered structure; hence, reaching the interlayer area becomes exceedingly challenging [66]. This component results in the minimal swelling of kaolinite soil. When xanthan gum is introduced to kaolinite soil, the hydrophilic xanthan gum hydrogels absorb infiltrating pore liquids, resulting in swelling [67]. The swelling of xanthan-stabilized soil increases marginally for this reason (Fig. 10a). The swelling of the stabilized kaolinite sample rose from 9.1 % to 14.57 % relative to its unstabilized condition. Bentonite soil consists of montmorillonite clay, characterized by a 2:1 layer with an octahedral sheet interposed between two silica sheets. The presence of interlayer water and exchangeable cations inside the montmorillonite layers causes the soil to expand upon water absorption. The swelling and distortion of bentonite result from the repellent forces between its two layers [68]. This component results in a significant propensity for bentonite soil to expand. Incorporating xanthan gum into bentonite soil reduced swelling from 274 % to 186 %, showing an 88 % drop in the stabilized sample. Consequently, the bentonite particles aggregate by xanthan gum monomer, enhance the particle size of the soil, and diminish its specific surface area [48]. The drop in the specific surface area of the soil permits water to penetrate fewer layers, thereby reducing soil swelling (Fig. 10b). Despite the substantial reduction in bentonite soil swelling due to xanthan gum addition, complete control has not been achieved. Utilizing xanthan-stabilized bentonite in the subgrade of roads and railways, landfills, and the foundational layers of embankments and slopes subjected to substantial loads can resolve this issue. The application of the ideal dosage of xanthan gum in both bentonite and kaolinite showed that this biopolymer could greatly boost mechanical strength, according to the compressive and swelling tests.

As visual observation demonstrated from SEM images, by covering clay particles and filling up spaces, specific surface area is reduced and xanthan gum works with bentonite to physically prevent water molecules from penetrating the clay layers. It should be mentioned that 2D SEM images were provided, which may not fully represent the material's 3D structure. Calculating the specific surface area from 2D SEM may cause some errors in dimension measuring. In addition, surface roughness or sub-micron pores might not be visible in 2D SEM images, leading to an underestimation of specific surface area. Furthermore, the bonding activity of the gum enhances the shear strength of the kaolinite and bentonite soils. Because xanthan gum bonds clay particles more firmly, the soil can endure greater shear pressures thus increasing the frictional resistance.

3.4. Durability under F-T cycles

As shown in Fig. 11, all samples had weight loss after completing F-T

Fig. 5. Stress-strain curves of xanthan stabilized-kaolinite: (a) 1 day (c) 7 days, (e) 14 days, (g) 28 days, (i) 56 days, and xanthan stabilized-bentonite: (b) 1 day (d) 7 days, (f) 14 days, (h) 28 days, (j) 56 days.

Fig. 6. Schematic illustration of xanthan function in soil.

Fig. 7. Trend of E₅₀ changes at varying percentages of xanthan and different curing times.

Fig. 8. Failure modes of samples: (a) kaolinite, (b) stabilized kaolinite with 28 days curing, (c) bentonite, and (d) stabilized bentonite with 28 days curing.

cycles. However, the samples stabilized with xanthan gum exhibited a notably lower degree of weight loss. More precisely, the untreated kaolinite and bentonite soils experienced weight losses of 4.1 gr and 3.7 gr, respectively. Meanwhile, the xanthan-stabilized samples showed weight losses of 1.58 gr and 1.3 gr after 10 cycles for the two types of soil. The variation in weight loss between kaolinite and bentonite soils can be attributed to the more porous structure of the kaolinite soil. This structure exhibits significantly lower resistance to F-T cycles in its unstabilized condition. The enhanced durability of stabilized soils, characterized by decreased mass loss, can be attributed to the cohesive properties of the hydrogels. These gels form between soil particles and establish interconnections that bind the particles together. Therefore, the robust gelling capabilities of xanthan gum have a notable impact on enhancing soil durability.

Fig. 12 shows that the compressive strength of the samples decreased similarly to their weight. Regardless of the type of soil, the UCS of the samples was reduced by increasing the F-T cycles. The most significant compressive strength drop for both soil types occurred during the initial cycle, consistent with the findings of Salimi et al. [69]. Furthermore, as illustrated in Fig. 12, the decline in compressive strength from cycles 7 to 10 indicated a more gradual trend. Through preparing trial samples, it was established that there was little variation in compressive strength after 10 cycles; hence, it was selected as the final cycle. After completing 10 cycles, the UCS of unstabilized kaolinite reduced significantly from 305 kPa to 41.73 kPa, indicating an 86 % reduction. The strength of the unstabilized bentonite reduced from 686 kPa to 288 kPa, indicating a 58 % decline. Adding xanthan gum to the soil led to a 44.51 % loss of UCS for kaolinite after completing 10 cycles. In contrast, the reduction in UCS

Fig. 9. Swelling characteristics of (a) Kaolinite soil and (b) Bentonite soil.

Fig. 10. Schematic of swelling potential: (a) Kaolinite and (b) Bentonite.

for stabilized bentonite was 31.42 %. It is worth mentioning that in the freezing process, the formation of ice crystals leads to expansion between soil particles and increases their size. In other words, freezing occurs when water in the soil freezes and expands, pushing soil particles upward. The expansion of frozen water can displace soil and any structures over it [70]. On the other side, in the thawing cycle, the frozen water in the soil matrix melts and causes soil shrinkage. When the soil matrix thaws, water from the melted ice often has nowhere to drain, leading to saturated conditions [71]. Saturated soil has much lower strength, making it susceptible to compression and settlement. Generally, a continuous F-T cycle causes successive ice formation and melting, which create porous areas and initiate cracking. As a result of the sequence of this process, the porous material created weakens the structure and integrity of the soil matrix and leads to a reduction in soil

strength. However, the incorporation of xanthan gum into the soil occupied the voids between soil particles, and the formation of a bio-crystallized structure impeded water infiltration into the soil matrix.

3.5. Ultrasonic testing

Fig. 13 shows that adding xanthan gum to the soil increased the stiffness of the stabilized samples. After a curing period of 28 days, a sticky gel is formed. This gel transforms into suspended crystalline particles and fills the empty spaces in the soil. Filling voids leads to the formation of a more uniform substance within the soil structure, resulting in enhanced soil compactness. This process has been documented in previous studies on soil stabilization [72,73]. In this respect, the biopolymer filled the empty spaces in the soil with xanthan gum

Fig. 11. Weight loss trend after application of the F-T cycles: (a) Kaolinite soil and (b) Bentonite soil.

Fig. 12. Compressive strength changes trend of (a) unstabilized and (b) xanthan-stabilized samples after applying successive F-T cycles.

hydrogels. Thus, the velocity of compression waves within the samples increased from 421 and 821 $\frac{m}{s}$ for untreated soil to 969 and 1364 $\frac{m}{s}$ for those treated with 1 % xanthan gum and 28 days of curing for kaolinite and bentonite, respectively. Consequently, the stiffness levels of treated soil increased (Fig. 14). Conversely, when the curing time increases, the existing hydrogels become more rigid, increasing the stiffness of the samples.

Fig. 15 depicts a decrease in the stiffness of the samples during multiple F-T cycles. This reduction in stiffness for untreated bentonite and kaolinite was from 1223 and 340 to 390 MPa and 133 MPa, respectively. Meanwhile, in samples stabilized with xanthan gum, the decrease in stiffness is also evident. However, because of the presence of xanthan gum and the links it establishes between soil particles, this loss is smaller than in untreated soil. More precisely, the stiffness of bentonite stabilized with xanthan gum dropped from 3323 to 1321 MPa. The stiffness of kaolinite stabilized with 1 % xanthan decreased from

1753 to 766 MPa. The F-T process results in soil's contraction and expansion, increasing the gaps between soil particles. Compressive waves move slower in gas and liquid environments compared to solid environments. As the number of voids increases, the velocity of these waves in the samples declines.

3.6. Effect of temperature

The impact of temperature on the resistance of the samples was determined by subjecting the samples to temperatures of 40, 70, and 100 °C for 28 days. Fig. 16 shows that samples stored at 70 °C had the maximum strength, while those stored at 100 °C had the lowest strength. At a temperature of 70 °C, xanthan's microorganisms exhibited an intensified activity, resulting in a higher frequency of interactions among these particles [60]. Thus, the greater the number of interactions, the stronger the gel will be. Accordingly, it improves the adhesion

Fig. 13. Effect of xanthan content on soil stiffness for (a) Kaolinite and (b) Bentonite.

Fig. 14. Schematic of the compression wave motion path before and after stabilization.

Fig. 15. Stiffness changes of (a) Kaolinite and (b) Bentonite clays after applying F-T cycles.

Fig. 16. Compressive strength of samples cured at different temperatures: (a) Kaolinite soil and (b) Bentonite soil.

between xanthan gum and soil particles, ultimately enhancing the strength of the samples. Indeed, kaolinite and bentonite soils treated with 1 % xanthan gum and then cured in an oven for 28 days exhibited improvements of 39 % and 94 %, respectively, compared to identically treated samples left at room temperature. These findings indicate that bentonite outperforms kaolinite at a temperature of 70 °C. Besides, as the temperature reaches 100 °C, the microorganisms in the samples begin to degrade due to the high temperature. The deterioration of these particles diminishes the cohesive connections established between xanthan gum and clay soil, resulting in the samples losing their resilience.

3.7. Microstructural studies

3.7.1. XRD

Fig. 17a and 17b exhibit the XRD patterns of untreated kaolinite and bentonite samples, as well as those stabilized with xanthan gum and cured for 28 days. The XRD patterns indicate that the principal mineral constituents of kaolinite and bentonite clay comprise silica (S), aluminum (A), calcium oxide (Ca), and iron (I) minerals. XRD analysis and microscopic examination indicated that the clay particles are primarily plate-shaped, with their edges predominantly showing prismatic forms. Thus, the primary and predominant peaks detected suggest that most clay particles are stacked in layers, consistent with the findings of Žbik et al. [74]. The minerals comprising kaolinite and bentonite are mainly silica and aluminum phases. These minerals lead to a peak in the XRD curve due to electron interaction with silica and aluminum

Fig. 17. XRD patterns of (a) Kaolinite and stabilized kaolinite and (b) Bentonite and stabilized bentonite.

minerals. On the other hand, incorporating the xanthan gum into kaolinite and bentonite soil samples does not result in a notable alteration of the primary peak angles. The primary peaks in the XRD curve remain unchanged with the incorporation of xanthan gum into the specified soils. This result is explained by the filling effect of the xanthan biopolymer resulting from hydrogen bonding. In other words, in both soils, a minor shift between peaks happens as results of hydrogen bonding. Moreover, the xanthan gum content employed in this work functioned as a conventional filler between the silica and aluminum layers, influencing the silica layers' interaction. Besides, soil stabilization with xanthan gum increases the intensity of the primary peaks. This enhancement is more significant in bentonite soil than kaolinite soil because of superior water absorption and increased hydrogen bonding. In summary, inert biopolymer does not undergo phase transitions as they only increase the intensity of the peaks [75].

Biopolymers display bio-adhesive characteristics due to their natural origin and inert attributes when mixed with water or hydrogen and oxygen molecules (H_2O). This is opposed to the conventional stabilizers that promote hydration and pozzolanic interactions among soil particles and chemical additives. Hence adding xanthan gum to the kaolinite and bentonite soils generates the only intermolecular forces such as hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interactions, ionic interactions, and van der Waals, which fundamentally induce biochemical alterations. Thus, it led to notable alterations in hydromechanical properties such as shear and compressive attributed to hydrogen bonding within the clay [75, 76].

3.7.2. FTIR

Fig. 18 shows the FTIR spectrum, exhibiting characteristic absorption signals associated with kaolinite and bentonite in both unstabilized and stabilized with 1% xanthan gum and cured for 28 days. The Si-O-Al group is identified at around 795, 700, and 534 cm^{-1} ; the Al-OH group at 911 cm^{-1} ; the Si-O group at 1080, 1030, and 1007 cm^{-1} ; and the -OH group at 3694, 3664, 3648, and 3621 cm^{-1} . Concerning the -OH absorption bands ranging from 3694 to 3620 cm^{-1} , external -OH signals are detected at 3621 cm^{-1} , while internal -OH signals are identified at 3694, 3664, and 3648 cm^{-1} . Compared to kaolinite soil, the FTIR spectra of both composites exhibit absorption signals ranging from roughly 1170 to 930 cm^{-1} (overlapping C—O stretching), 2866 cm^{-1} (symmetric C—H stretching), and 2908 cm^{-1} . Furthermore, the carbon and hydrogen stretches' (asymmetric C—H stretching) indicate the

functional groups of organic constituents inside the composite structures. Additionally, in the stabilized soils, the FTIR signals at 1615 cm^{-1} are ascribed to carboxylate anions (C = O stretching vibration). The spectra of these composites exhibit rather broad hydrogen bond signals attributable to hydroxyl groups and carboxylate anions in xanthan gum, along with surface-adsorbed water. The specified characteristic signals denote the existence of organic constituents (in xanthan gum) inside the soil composite structures.

3.7.3. SEM and EDS

Fig. 19 shows the SEM images of unstabilized soils and those stabilized with different concentrations of xanthan gum and cured for 28 days. According to Fig. 19a and 19b, the kaolinite and bentonite clay samples possess several weak sheets characterized by a scattered structure and elevated water absorption capacity. The lamellar structure of bentonite clay is evident due to its swelling characteristics. The kaolinite and bentonite clay samples have a multilayer structure, resulting in soil particles with significant water absorption capacity and nano-sized holes. This multilayered arrangement generates substantial voids among the soil particles. The proliferation of these pores finally diminishes the samples' strength, corroborating the findings of the UCS tests performed in this study. Fig. 19c–h present the SEM images of soil stabilized with 0.5–2% XG content following a 28-day curing duration. Fig. 19c and 19d demonstrate the production of flocculated particles in samples stabilized with 0.5% xanthan biopolymer. This product is attributed to cation exchange processes, bio-gel, and bio-crystal interactions during both short and long durations. At low xanthan concentrations (0.5%), evidence of aggregation is seen in the soil structure, accompanied by pore spaces within the aggregates and limited xanthan gel covering. In other words, at low concentrations, xanthan gum acted as a mild stabilizer. The xanthan gum molecules bound the soil particles together, promoting slight aggregation without fully coating all particles. As shown in Fig. 19c and 19d, the addition of small amounts of xanthan gum slightly reduced soil porosity as it filled some void spaces. However, it did not alter the natural structure significantly. It should be noted that low concentrations help to increase stability by forming a slight binding film around particles, making it more resistant to stress without heavily compacting the soil.

Following an increase in xanthan gum content (specifically at 1%), the soil matrix exhibits greater density, indicating soil particle coverage by the resultant gel (Fig. 19e and 19f). Consequently, over time, at the

Fig. 18. FTIR spectra of (a) Kaolinite and stabilized kaolinite and (b) Bentonite and stabilized bentonite.

Fig. 19. SEM micrographs of (a) Kaolinite, (b) Bentonite, (c) Kaolinite+0.5 %XG, (d) Bentonite+0.5 %XG, (e) Kaolinite+1 %XG, (f) Bentonite+1 %XG, (g) Kaolinite+2 %XG and (h) Bentonite+2 %XG.

ideal xanthan gum concentration (1 %), cementitious reactions between clay particles and additives result in the development of a bio-gel. The bio-gel occupies the interstices between clay particles (including both bentonite and kaolinite) and functions as a polymeric medium among them. Xanthan-stabilized samples exhibit a bio-gel within soil pores, forming a robust connection among soil particles, thereby diminishing voids relative to unstabilized samples. Xanthan gum particles occupy the pores and augment the efficacy of intermolecular forces, including electrostatic, polar, hydrogen, and ionic forces. These particles facilitate the development of supplementary bio-cementitious gels (Fig. 19c and 19d). Furthermore, the analyzed soils include both positive and negative ions on the surfaces of soil particles. These ions enhance the interaction between soil particles and bio-xanthan by generating forces, electrostatic interactions, and cation exchange capacity. These forces enhance the uniformity of soil performance and augment friction, adhesion, and contact among soil particles. Moreover, xanthan gum improves the adherence of cementitious products to surfaces, promoting optimal bonding with the soil. Fig. 19f shows that the presence of this bio-gel results in bio-covering, bio-encapsulating, bio-crusting, and bio-coating on the surface. As a result, it improves the mechanical strength and durability of the samples, particularly inside bentonite soil layers [59]. At this level, xanthan gum begins to form a thicker network around soil particles, effectively bridging them and leading to better particle aggregation. Moderate concentrations reduce soil porosity more notably. The xanthan gum creates a more substantial binding matrix, which partially fills micro-pores between particles. Xanthan gum enhances the soil's cohesive strength, making it more compact. This increased cohesion also decreases soil erosion, creating a more durable structure. SEM images show that with increased xanthan gum concentration, soil particles appear more aggregated. Xanthan gum forms a network that binds particles, creating denser clusters and reducing their spacing. This binding effect improves cohesion and reduces the likelihood of particle displacement under stress. The addition of xanthan gum tends to fill the voids between soil particles, resulting in a tighter, more compact structure. SEM images reveal smaller, more uniformly distributed pores at higher xanthan gum concentrations, which reduces soil permeability.

Meanwhile, when the concentration of xanthan gum exceeds the optimum threshold of 1 %, the xanthan gum structure within the soil matrix becomes increasingly aggregated. Consequently, it intensifies xanthan-xanthan interactions and generates interstitial space (Fig. 19g and 19h). In other words, at high concentrations, higher xanthan gum reduces the contact between soil and bio-gel and increases the contact between bio-gel and bio-gel, which reduces the frictional and interlocking forces in the soil matrix.

EDS analysis was employed to show the range of elements present in xanthan-stabilized soils (Fig. 20a–d). As xanthan gum is mixed with soil, EDS spectra typically show an increase in carbon (C) and oxygen (O) peaks, indicating the presence of xanthan gum on soil particles. This organic coating, which appears more pronounced at higher concentrations (1 %), suggests a consistent xanthan gum distribution across the soil matrix. The presence of xanthan gum's organic coating as observed in EDS leads to improved cohesion and bonding between particles, providing resistance to shear forces and increasing compressive strength. The denser elemental distribution contributes to this mechanical improvement by limiting particle mobility. The EDS examination of unstabilized samples reveals that silica (Si) and aluminum (Al) are the major constituents of the soil. EDS analysis of xanthan-stabilized soil shows a novel element, C, which constitutes the primary constituent of xanthan gum (Fig. 20b and 20d). This element indicates the existence of xanthan gum within the permeable composition of the soil. Also, it facilitates water absorption and triggers biological responses in the soil. The combination of hydrogen and Si and Al element is responsible for gel production in the soil structure, considering its ability to absorb and retain water. In other words, as xanthan gum concentration reaches the optimum dosage in bentonite and kaolinite, EDS reveals a thicker

coating of carbon and oxygen across soil particles. This coating represents xanthan gum's gel-like presence around soil particles, creating a binding layer contributing to mechanical reinforcement (Fig. 20e and 20f). Furthermore, in kaolinite and benitoite soil high amount of Si and Al levels leads to higher interaction between soil particles and xanthan gum due to the presence of Al^{3+} in the octahedral sites and Si^{4+} in the tetrahedral sites [77,78]. The reason is ion bridging, where silica ions bond with xanthan gum's carboxyl groups, improving the strength and stability of the soil matrix. It is worth mentioning that by comparing the EDS patterns of kaolinite and bentonite and EDS mapping after adding 1 % XG in both soils, no new chemical compound is found.

4. Life cycle assessment (LCA)

Conducting a life cycle assessment is a popular method that is utilized to analyze the cost-effectiveness, efficacy, and sustainability capabilities of materials. In this evaluation, specific advantages of xanthan gum are presented compared to traditional stabilizers such as cement or lime, focusing on environmental benefits and potential cost-effectiveness. In large-scale applications in certain places, the expenses associated with conventional stabilizers (e.g., lime, gypsum, cement, and bitumen) might be up to three times larger than those of xanthan gum. Additionally, the expenses related to the conventional stabilizers may be significantly higher due to their higher dosage. This is especially true when it comes to transportation over large distances to construction sites [23]. In comparison to the past, the price of xanthan gum has dramatically fallen in recent years as a result of the increased utilization of xanthan gum in the cosmetic, hygiene, food, and medical industries. Hence, the cost of employing 1 ton of xanthan decreased from around \$250 to \$25 over the past three decades [79], which is a reduction of approximately \$225. This issue indicates that the cost of this biopolymer will further decrease in the future, because of its multiple uses. It should also be noted that this price is specifically for pure xanthan gum powder, however, lower purity is sufficient for soil stabilization.

On the other hand, the recent utilization of traditional stabilizers and calcium-based substances for soil modification may have adverse effects on human health owing to their harmful environmental impacts. For instance, during the calcination process, lime is produced along with carbon dioxide when heat is applied to limestone. Indeed, to produce 1 ton of lime, 1.0 to 1.8 tons of CO_2 is produced and released into the atmosphere [80], of which 68 % is caused by chemical reactions, 30 % by fuel combustion, and 2 % is caused by electricity consumption [81]. Stabilizing 100 kg of soil requires approximately 5 kg of lime. Using 5 kg of lime to stabilize 100 kg of soil results in the emission of 5 to 9 kg of CO_2 . According to previous studies [59,82], for every ton of cement produced, one ton of carbon dioxide is released into the atmosphere. Considering that stabilizing 100 kg of soil requires 6 kg of cement, stabilizing this amount of soil with cement results in the emission of 5–6 kg of CO_2 . Furthermore, the stabilization of soil with bitumen has also negative environmental impacts due to the resulting CO_2 [83]. Producing one ton of bitumen releases between 510 and 828 kg of CO_2 into the atmosphere [84]. The use of this material to stabilize 100 kg of soil results in the emission of 2–3.2 kg of CO_2 into the atmosphere. The amount of xanthan gum necessary for soil stabilization is considerably less than that required for conventional additives. One kg of xanthan gum is necessary to stabilize 100 kg of soil. Stabilizing 100 kg of soil with xanthan gum results in carbon dioxide emissions ranging from 0.9 to 1.3, which is much lower than the amount of carbon dioxide produced by traditional additives. Based on these findings, xanthan is an appropriate option in terms of both cost and sustainability, in addition to being ecologically friendly in comparison to conventional additives (Table 4 and Fig. 21).

5. Practical implications and consideration

The present study's findings suggest that soil stabilization with

Fig. 20. EDS patterns of (a) Kaolinite, (b) Kaolinite+1 %XG, (c) Bentonite, (d) Bentonite+1 %XG and EDS mapping of (e) Kaolinite+1 %XG, (f) Bentonite+1 %XG.

Table 4
Cost for xanthan gum and other conventional binders to stabilize soil.

Additives	Xanthan gum	Cement	Lime	Bitumen
Method of implementation	Direct injection and spraying	Grouting, deep injection and spraying	Grouting and spraying	Spraying and injection
Price for 1 ton soil stabilization (USD)	25–250	85–150	60–110	150–200

xanthan gum has the potential to be employed in a variety of ge-engineering projects. In a large-scale study of road construction in Sri Lanka, it was found that the cyclic compressive strength of pavement is significantly improved up to 50 % [23]. Moreover, the utilization of xanthan gum in subgrade can be an alternative to diminish the thickness of subgrade and asphalt pavements. This study suggested that the deformations caused by the pressures applied to the sublayers of roads and railroads can be dramatically controlled by xanthan gum application on a field scale [23]. In another large-scale application, it was found that the compressive strength after 28 days of curing can reach more than 1 MPa, which, according to FHWA standards, is desirable for a stabilized subgrade layer and soil matrix [85,86]. Another field application of

xanthan gum is linked to the conservation and stability of soil in river-side trenches, which is a critical concern [87]. Stabilizing kaolinite soil while managing swelling in bentonite soil can improve the cohesiveness of soil particles and the stability of the embankment and slope (Fig. 22a). The application of xanthan gum in riverbanks in a real-world project proved that the erosion caused by water can reduce up to 65 % [87]. In another large-scale application in Korea, in a sand dune, it was found that the utilization of xanthan gum hydrogel aggregated soil particles and mitigated soil erosion up to 70 % under 30 to 50 $\frac{m}{s}$ wind speeds [88]. Furthermore, the landfill’s outer layer must be impermeable to water, wind, and weather while adhering to the region’s environmental and ecological restrictions. Utilizing xanthan gum as an economic alternative liner in clay soil in a case study proved that it can mitigate soil erosion, thus preserving the integrity of the surface layer. Additionally, it was also found that after 120 days of curing, leachate and hydraulic conductivity decreased by 2.72×10^5 folds [89] (Fig. 22b).

According to previous research xanthan gum-stabilized soil performs well in extreme environmental conditions, such as high and low pH, drought and saturated conditions, and saline and hypersaline environments [47,59,87,90]. In high humidity, xanthan gum helps maintain soil structure by binding particles together, reducing the risk of erosion and compaction. It enhances water retention, allowing the soil to manage excess moisture without becoming overly saturated. Furthermore, xanthan gum enhances shear strength and interparticle adhesion [50]. In

Fig. 21. Comparing the CO₂ emission for xanthan gum and other conventional binders to stabilize 100 kg soil.

Fig. 22. Practical and executive utilizations of xanthan-stabilized kaolinite and bentonite: (a) embankment and (b) landfill.

dry, semi-arid, and highly degradable areas, the introduction of xanthan gum decreases severe surface erosion and land degradation. In arid areas, xanthan gum binds the soil by directly interacting with the outer layer of the charged clay particles in the geo-matrix, minimizing water loss and increasing the soil's ability to retain water. In saline environments, xanthan gum can mitigate the adverse effects of salinity. It aids in the retention of moisture and nutrients, helping plants to better cope with salt stress [91]. The presence of xanthan gum can improve soil aggregation, which can enhance drainage and reduce salt accumulation in the root zone. Overall, xanthan-stabilized soil shows resilience in extreme conditions, while improving its physical properties and supporting plant growth even in extreme environments [92].

6. Conclusions and future trends

The main goal of the present research was to evaluate the addition of xanthan gum biopolymer to improve various properties of kaolinite and bentonite soils with different swelling potentials. Effects of xanthan gum were compared on the specific characteristics of kaolinite and bentonite soils. The findings indicated that the mechanical properties and durability of kaolinite and bentonite soils were greatly influenced by soil stabilization with xanthan gum biopolymer. The main results of this research are:

1. The optimum concentration of xanthan gum (1 %) in bentonite and kaolinite soils created sticky bio-gels with compressive strengths of 1032 and 1712 kPa after 28 days of curing. Additionally, adding xanthan gum to both soils reduced MDD due to lower dry density and increased OMC due to water affinity.
2. Incorporating xanthan gum with bentonite soil reduced swelling 88 %. Xanthan gum hydrogels cover bentonite soil particles, lowering their surface area. Adding xanthan gum to kaolinite soil increased its swelling by 6 %. Since kaolinite has a poor water absorption rate, xanthan gum particles absorb water into the stabilized matrix, increasing swelling.
3. F-T resistance of bentonite and kaolinite soils increased up to 24 % and 44 % after 10 cycles by the introduction of xanthan gum. The bio-gel improves soil particle adhesion and results in the transformation of xanthan gum hydrogels into crystalline particles during curing. It means that less water can infiltrate into the soil matrix and lower the continuous evaporation and freezing of water molecules.
4. The compressive strength of stabilized soils with 1 % xanthan gum and curing at 70 °C for 28 days reached 1423 and 3329 kPa for kaolinite and bentonite, respectively. Due to the higher cohesive contact, bio gel and soil particles adhered more effectively, increasing strength. By increasing the temperature from 70 to 100 °C, microorganisms in the samples start to disintegrate due to high heat which diminished bonding.
5. UPV results showed that adding xanthan gum increased soil stiffness by filling small empty spaces and increasing compression wave velocity. Furthermore, microstructural analysis revealed that the addition of xanthan gum to soils induced the formation of bio-gel and created a bridge between the particles.

This study showed that xanthan gum, an eco-friendly ingredient, can substantially stabilize clayey soils. However, pH and the performance of xanthan gum in alkaline and acidic environments, xanthan gum's resistance to corrosion, and the impact of different moisture levels in the environment also affect the mechanical properties of xanthan-stabilized soil, which were not examined in this study. Additionally, conducting large-scale tests could be a suitable option to assess the feasibility of using stabilized kaolinite and bentonite clays in construction projects. Furthermore, it is also essential to study the treatment of clay and examine the impact of cyclic loading on the behavior of the xanthan gum-soil matrix.

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Sahand Fateh: Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Yasaman Mansourkiaei:** Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohammad Mahdi Shalchian:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mahyar Arabani:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Meghdad Payan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Payam Zanganeh Ranjbar:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] F. Darikandeh, B. Viswanadham, M. Arabani, Small-scale laboratory test on expansive soil stabilized by CCR-Fly ash columns, *Proceed. Institut. Civil Eng.-Ground Improv.* 175 (1) (2022) 64–72.
- [2] Z. Adamis, R.B. Williams, Bentonite, kaolin, and Selected Clay Minerals, *World health organization*, 2005.
- [3] N. Akhmediyeva, et al., Kaolinite clay as a raw material for erbium extraction, *Heliyon* 9 (4) (2023).
- [4] P.V. Sivapullaiah, A.A.B. Moghal, Role of gypsum in the strength development of fly ashes with lime, *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* 23 (2) (2011) 197–206.
- [5] K.V. Vydehi, A.A.B. Moghal, Effect of biopolymeric stabilization on the strength and compressibility characteristics of cohesive soil, *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* 34 (2) (2022) 04021428.
- [6] M. Arabani, M.M. Shalchian, M.M. Rahimabadi, Use of wheat fiber and nanobentonite to stabilize clay subgrades, *Results Eng.* (2024) 102931.
- [7] M. Hamza, et al., Geotechnical behavior of high-plastic clays treated with biopolymer: macro-micro-study, *Environ. Earth Sci.* 82 (3) (2023) 91.
- [8] M. Salimi, et al., Impact of clay nano-material and glass fiber on the efficacy of traditional soil stabilization technique, *Mater. Lett.* 360 (2024) 136046.
- [9] E. Worrell, et al., Carbon dioxide emissions from the global cement industry, *Annu. Rev. Energy Env.* 26 (1) (2001) 303–329.
- [10] H. Yang, et al., A comprehensive overview of geopolymer composites: a bibliometric analysis and literature review, *Case Studies in Construct. Mater.* 16 (2022) e00830.
- [11] C. Yao, et al., Prediction on the freeze-thaw resistance of a one-part geopolymer stabilized soil by using deep learning method, *Case Studies Construct. Mater.* 21 (2024) e03530.
- [12] M. Hamza, et al., Geotechnical properties of problematic expansive subgrade stabilized with xanthan gum biopolymer, *Road Materials and Pavement Design* 24 (7) (2023) 1869–1883.
- [13] M. Arabani, M.M. Shalchian, M.M. Rahimabadi, The influence of rice fiber and nanoclay on mechanical properties and mechanisms of clayey soil stabilization, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 407 (2023) 133542.
- [14] I. Bozyigit, A. Javadi, S. Altun, Strength properties of xanthan gum and guar gum treated kaolin at different water contents, *J. Rock Mech. Geotechn. Eng.* 13 (5) (2021) 1160–1172.
- [15] E. Kasehchi, M.A. Arjomand, M.H.A. Elizei, Experimental investigation of the feasibility of stabilizing inshore silty sand soil using geopolymer based on ceramic waste powder: an approach to upcycling waste material for sustainable construction, *Case Studies Construct. Mater.* 20 (2024) e02979.
- [16] M. Arabani, M.M. Rahimabadi, M.M. Shalchian, Combined effects of barley fibers and nanoclay on clayey soil stabilization, *Geotech. Geol. Eng.* (2024) 1–24.
- [17] M. Arabani, M.M. Shalchian, A review of the use of bio-based substances in soil stabilization, *Environ., Dev. Sustain.* 26 (6) (2024) 13685–13737.
- [18] B. Aaliya, K.V. Sunooj, M. Lackner, Biopolymer composites: a review, *Int. J. Biobased Plastics* 3 (1) (2021) 40–84.

- [19] M.K. Sangdeh, et al., Predicting the precipitated calcium carbonate and unconfined compressive strength of bio-mediated sands through robust hybrid optimization algorithms, *Transportation Geotechnics* 46 (2024) 101235.
- [20] R. Acharya, et al., Assessment of guar gum biopolymer treatment toward mitigation of desiccation cracking on slopes built with expansive soils, *Transp. Res. Rec.* 2657 (1) (2017) 78–88.
- [21] O. Etemadi, et al., Stabilization of metals in subsurface by biopolymers: laboratory drainage flow studies, *Soil. Sediment. Contam.* 12 (5) (2003) 647–661.
- [22] J. Ni, et al., Performance of soils enhanced with eco-friendly biopolymers in unconfined compression strength tests and fatigue loading tests, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 263 (2020) 120039.
- [23] S. Lee, et al., Xanthan gum biopolymer as soil-stabilization binder for road construction using local soil in Sri Lanka, *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* 31 (11) (2019) 06019012.
- [24] A.A.B. Moghal, K.V. Vydehi, State-of-the-art review on efficacy of xanthan gum and guar gum inclusion on the engineering behavior of soils, *Innovat. Infrastruct. Solut.* 6 (2021) 1–14.
- [25] F. Garcia-Ochoa, et al., Xanthan gum: production, recovery, and properties, *Biotechnol. Adv.* 18 (7) (2000) 549–579.
- [26] E.R. Sujatha, et al., Enhancing the geotechnical properties of soil using xanthan gum—An eco-friendly alternative to traditional stabilizers, *Bull. Eng. Geol. Environ.* 80 (2021) 1157–1167.
- [27] B. Bağrıaçık, B. Mahmutluoğlu, Conducting large-scale model experiments on xanthan gum treated clay as an eco-friendly approach to soil improvement, *KSCCE J. Civ. Eng.* 27 (4) (2023) 1480–1489.
- [28] Z. Chen, et al., Wetting–drying effects on the mechanical performance of xanthan gum biopolymer-stabilized soil, *Environ. Earth. Sci.* 83 (7) (2024) 197.
- [29] Y. Wu, et al., Improving the impermeability and mechanical properties of the Yellow River sediment with polymer gels, *Case Studies Construct. Mater.* 20 (2024) e03246.
- [30] J.R. Joga, B. Varaprasad, Sustainable improvement of expansive clays using xanthan gum as a biopolymer, *Civ. Eng. J* 5 (9) (2019) 1893–1903.
- [31] J. Ma, et al., Ultra-compressed earth block stabilized by bio-binder for sustainable building construction, *Case Studies in Construct. Mater.* 21 (2024) e03523.
- [32] C. Galán-Marín, C. Rivera-Gómez, J. Petric, Clay-based composite stabilized with natural polymer and fibre, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 24 (8) (2010) 1462–1468.
- [33] H.R. Khatami, B.C. O’Kelly, Improving mechanical properties of sand using biopolymers, *J. Geotech. Geoenviron. Eng.* 139 (8) (2013) 1402–1406.
- [34] N. Latifi, et al., Xanthan gum biopolymer: an eco-friendly additive for stabilization of tropical organic peat, *Environ. Earth. Sci.* 75 (2016) 1–10.
- [35] A.S.A. Rashid, et al., Sustainable improvement of tropical residual soil using an environmentally friendly additive, *Geotech. Geol. Eng.* 35 (2017) 2613–2623.
- [36] N. Hataf, P. Ghadir, N. Ranjbar, Investigation of soil stabilization using chitosan biopolymer, *J. Clean. Prod.* 170 (2018) 1493–1500.
- [37] H. Sulaiman, et al., Performance of soil stabilized with biopolymer materials—xanthan gum and guar gum, *Phys. Chem. Earth, Parts A/B/C* 128 (2022) 103276.
- [38] M. Hamza, et al., Strengthening potential of xanthan gum biopolymer in stabilizing weak subgrade soil, *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* 24 (9) (2022) 2719–2738.
- [39] P. Bagheri, I. Gratchev, M. Rybachuk, Effects of xanthan gum biopolymer on soil mechanical properties, *Appl. Sci.* 13 (2) (2023) 887.
- [40] N. Latifi, et al., Improvement of problematic soils with biopolymer—An environmentally friendly soil stabilizer, *J. Mater. Civ. Eng.* 29 (2) (2017) 04016204.
- [41] ASTM, D.-. Standard test methods for liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index of soils. D4318–10, 2010.
- [42] D. ASTM, Standard Practice For Classification of Soils Forengineering Purposes (Unified Soil Classification System), D2487, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2011, p. 2011. www.ASTM.Org.
- [43] A. ASTM, Standard Test Method For Relative Density (specific gravity) and Absorption of Coarse Aggregate, ASTM West Conshohocken, PA, 2015.
- [44] Standard, A., D698, Standard Test Methods For Laboratory Compaction Characteristics of Soil Using Standard Effort, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2007.
- [45] D. ASTM, Standard Test Method For Unconfined Compressive Strength of Cohesive Soil, 2166, ASTM standard D, 2006.
- [46] D. Astm, Standard test method for direct shear test of soils under consolidated drained conditions, D3080/D3080M 3 (9) (2011).
- [47] I. Chang, et al., Effects of Xanthan gum biopolymer on soil strengthening, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 74 (2015) 65–72.
- [48] S.P. Singh, R. Das, Geo-engineering properties of expansive soil treated with xanthan gum biopolymer, *Geomech. Geoeng.* 15 (2) (2020) 107–122.
- [49] J.J. Reddy, B. Varaprasad, Long-term and durability properties of xanthan gum treated dispersive soils—An eco-friendly material, *Mater. Today: Proc.* 44 (2021) 309–314.
- [50] A. Soldo, M. Miletić, Study on shear strength of xanthan gum-amended soil, *Sustainability* 11 (21) (2019) 6142.
- [51] ASTM, ASTM C 597: Standard Test Method For Pulse Velocity Through Concrete, ASTM International, 2016, pp. 3–6.
- [52] T. Mandal, J.M. Tinjum, T.B. Edil, Non-destructive testing of cementitiously stabilized materials using ultrasonic pulse velocity test, *Transportat. Geotechn.* 6 (2016) 97–107.
- [53] N. Toohey, M. Mooney, Seismic modulus growth of lime-stabilised soil during curing, *Geotechnique* 62 (2) (2012) 161–170.
- [54] ASTM, D., Standard test methods for one-dimensional swell or collapse of soils. D4546–14, 2014.
- [55] D. ASTM, Standard test methods for freezing and thawing compacted soil-cement mixtures. ASTM D560, 2003.
- [56] T. Kamei, A. Ahmed, T. Shibi, Effect of freeze–thaw cycles on durability and strength of very soft clay soil stabilised with recycled Basanite, *Cold Reg. Sci. Technol.* 82 (2012) 124–129.
- [57] C. Liu, et al., Effects of freeze–thaw cycles on the unconfined compressive strength of straw fiber-reinforced soil, *Geotext. Geomembr.* 48 (4) (2020) 581–590.
- [58] A. Hotineanu, et al., Effect of freeze–thaw cycling on the mechanical properties of lime-stabilized expansive clays, *Cold Reg. Sci. Technol.* 119 (2015) 151–157.
- [59] M. Arabani, M.M. Shalchian, A. Baghbani, A state-of-the-art review on interactive mechanisms and multi-scale application of biopolymers (BPs) in geo-improvement and vegetation growth, *J. Environ. Manage.* 358 (2024) 120905.
- [60] I. Chang, G.-C. Cho, Strengthening of Korean residual soil with β -1, 3/1, 6-glucan biopolymer, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 30 (2012) 30–35.
- [61] S. Sabrin, S. Siddiqua, N. Muhammad, Understanding the effect of heat treatment on subgrade soil stabilized with bentonite and magnesium alkalization, *Transportation Geotechnics* 21 (2019) 100287.
- [62] D. Patwa, et al., Investigation of thermal and strength characteristics of a natural backfill composite inspired by synergistic biochar–biopolymer amendment of clay loam, *Can. Geotech. J.* 61 (6) (2023) 1073–1093.
- [63] Y.-M. Kwon1a, et al., Geotechnical engineering behavior of biopolymer-treated soft marine soil, *Geomech. Eng* 17 (2019) 453–464.
- [64] H. Dehghan, et al., Use of xanthan and guar gums in soil strengthening, *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* 21 (2019) 155–165.
- [65] I. Bozyigit, H.O. Zingil, S. Altun, Performance of eco-friendly polymers for soil stabilization and their resistance to freeze–thaw action, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 379 (2023) 131133.
- [66] C. Detellier, Functional kaolinite, *Chem. Record* 18 (7–8) (2018) 868–877.
- [67] Y.-M. Kwon, I. Chang, G.-C. Cho, Consolidation and swelling behavior of kaolinite clay containing xanthan gum biopolymer, *Acta Geotech.* 18 (7) (2023) 3555–3571.
- [68] H. Komine, N. Ogata, Predicting swelling characteristics of bentonites, *J. Geotech. Geoenviron. Eng.* 130 (8) (2004) 818–829.
- [69] M. Salimi, et al., Effect of glass fiber (GF) on the mechanical properties and freeze-thaw (FT) durability of lime-nanoclay (NC)-stabilized marl clayey soil, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 416 (2024) 135227.
- [70] K. Piechowicz, et al., Stabilization of Loose Soils as Part of Sustainable Development of Road Infrastructure, *Sustainability* 16 (9) (2024) 3592.
- [71] B. Dolinar, L. Trauner, The impact of structure on the undrained shear strength of cohesive soils, *Eng. Geol.* 92 (1–2) (2007) 88–96.
- [72] W. Sarro, G. Assis, G. Ferreira, Experimental investigation of the UPV wavelength in compacted soil, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 272 (2021) 121834.
- [73] I.H. Umar, H. Lin, A.S. Ibrahim, Laboratory testing and analysis of clay soil stabilization using waste marble powder, *Applied Sciences* 13 (16) (2023) 9274.
- [74] M.S. Žbik, et al., Kaolinite platelet orientation for XRD and AFM applications, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 50 (3) (2010) 299–304.
- [75] N. Latifi, et al., Strengthening montmorillonitic and kaolinitic clays using a calcium-based non-traditional additive: a micro-level study, *Appl. Clay Sci.* 132 (2016) 182–193.
- [76] H. Ghasemzadeh, F. Modiri, E. Darvishan, A novel clean biopolymer-based additive to improve mechanical and microstructural properties of clayey soil, *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy* (2022) 1–13.
- [77] N. Kumari, C. Mohan, Basics of clay minerals and their characteristic properties, *Clay Clay Miner* 24 (1) (2021).
- [78] Y.-M. Kwon, I. Chang, G.-C. Cho, Xanthan biopolymer-based soil treatment effect on kaolinite clay fabric and structure using XRD analysis, *Sci. Rep.* 13 (1) (2023) 11666.
- [79] I. Chang, J. Im, G.-C. Cho, Introduction of microbial biopolymers in soil treatment for future environmentally-friendly and sustainable geotechnical engineering, *Sustainability* 8 (3) (2016) 251.
- [80] M. Simoni, et al., Decarbonising the lime industry: state-of-the-art, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 168 (2022) 112765.
- [81] A. Dowling, J. O’Dwyer, C.C. Adley, Lime in the limelight, *J. Clean. Prod.* 92 (2015) 13–22.
- [82] E. Benhelal, et al., Global strategies and potentials to curb CO2 emissions in cement industry, *J. Clean. Prod.* 51 (2013) 142–161.
- [83] M. Arabani, et al., Enhancing mechanical properties of hot mix asphalt with olive kernel ash: a sustainable modifier, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 451 (2024) 138740.
- [84] M.I. Soiket, et al., Life cycle assessment of greenhouse gas emissions of upgrading and refining bitumen from the solvent extraction process, *Appl. Energy* 240 (2019) 236–250.
- [85] K.M. Briggs, F. Loveridge, S. Glendinning, Failures in transport infrastructure embankments, *Eng. Geol.* 219 (2017) 107–117.
- [86] M.F. Noaman, et al., Geotechnical and microstructural analysis of high-volume fly ash stabilized clayey soil and machine learning application, *Case Studies Construct. Mater.* 21 (2024) e03628.
- [87] A.A. Dubey, et al., Rheological properties of xanthan-gum solutions and their role in improving river embankments, *Geotech. Geol. Eng.* 42 (4) (2024) 2387–2401.
- [88] Y.-M. Kwon, et al., Xanthan gum biopolymer-based soil treatment as a construction material to mitigate internal erosion of earthen embankment: a field-scale, *Constr. Build. Mater.* 389 (2023) 131716.
- [89] A.K. Verma, A. Prasad, N.S. Bonal, Geotechnical performance of municipal solid waste fines stabilized with xanthan gum and agar gum, *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manage.* (2024) 1–18.

- [90] A. Mendonça, et al., A review on the importance of microbial biopolymers such as xanthan gum to improve soil properties, *Appl. Sci.* 11 (1) (2020) 170.
- [91] S. Wang, et al., Water retention characteristics and vegetation growth of biopolymer-treated silt soils, *Soil. Tillage Res.* 225 (2023) 105544.
- [92] J. Ni, et al., Mechanical and hydraulic characteristics of unvegetated or vegetated loess soils amended with xanthan gum, *Transportat. Geotech.* 48 (2024) 101350.